

Reuse of Peracetic Acid Bleach Bath for Bleaching of Different Ligno Cellulosic Fibres

S. N. Chattopadhyay*, Kartick K. Samanta, L. Ammayappan & R. K. Ghosh

Chemical & Biochemical Processing Division, ICAR-National Institute of Natural Fibre Engg. and Technology, Kolkata, WB

Abstract:

Our country several resources of plant fibres like jute, banana, ramie, flax, etc, which is grown in different parts and agro climatic zone and are having immense impact on the socioeconomic values. These fibres consist of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin as major constituents and due to their biodegradable and renewable in nature are becoming popular in textile and non-textile applications as a replacement of synthetic fibres and plastic items. Several diversified and value-added items are produced from these fibres like upholsteries, lifestyle products, varieties of fashion bags, handcrafts, etc along with mainstream products. So, chemical processing of these fibres has become essential and standardization of different unit operations like pre-treatments, bleaching, dyeing, printing, finishing, etc are needed to make them look beautiful and feel better. A few processes have been developed and require further modification for their sustainability. Bleaching is the heart of the chemical processing for all the subsequent processes are solely dependent on it for optimum results. Traditional bleaching using hydrogen peroxide is very popular in industry but along-with the achievement of high whiteness and brightness indices it results in substantial loss in tensile properties as the process is carried out at high alkaline condition as well as temperature, which damages these lignocellulosic fibres. So, an innovative peracetic acid bleaching process has been developed that is carried out at lower temperature in mild alkaline condition. Jute, banana, ramie and flax fibres contain cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin in different proportions in different fibres. Hence optimized condition of chemical processing varies for individual fibres. The peracetic acid bleaching process has been optimized for individual fibres using Taguchi Experimental Design (TED) and the optimized processes produces satisfactory whiteness/ brightness with high retention of tensile strength. To make the process sustainable, the left out bleach bath formulation has been re-claimed and it has been found that the left out liquor need to be used for further two batches of grey fibres to produce semi-bleached and quarter-bleached fibres which can be utilized for dyeing in variety of shades. The reuse of bleach bath can be done by different methodologies like compensation of bath or without. It is found that 1st reuse can be done without compensation but 2nd reuse produces better effect if compensation is done for liquor and pH correction.

Keywords: Banana, Bleaching, Fibre, Flax, Jute, Peracetic acid, Ramie, Reuse

*Corresponding Author:

Mr. S. N. Chattopadhyay
Chemical & Biochemical Processing Division
ICAR-National Institute of Natural Fibre Engineering and Technology
12 Regent Park,
Kolkata- 700 040, WB
E-mail: sambhu_in@yahoo.com

1. Introduction

India has different agro-climatic zones that exist in different parts of our country, and varieties of fibre yielding plants are available. Hence, India is blessed with a number of plants resources that produce different natural cellulose to lignocellulosic fibres. A few popular lignocellulosic fibres include jute, flax, ramie, banana, etc. are used for making different textile and non-textile product [1 - 4]. In the category of textile items, such fibre are used to produce coarse yarns, which are used for making packaging materials, low-cost bags, handicraft items

etc. and are mostly used for making low-value products cost [5]. The main advantages of these fibre-based products are biodegradable, environmentally friendly and annually renewable, so it has the potential to be used for making various value-added products. Recently lot of work has been carried out for development of processes which can produce finer yarns after suitable blending, advanced extraction process for obtaining finer fibres, chemical modification or treatment of fibre for making it softer, colouration of fibres with eco-friendly synthetic and natural dyes for making home textiles, upholsteries and even fashion or outer garments [6 - 9].

The cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin elemental composition varies from fibre to fibre, derived from the different plant sources. From the fibre chemical composition point of view, ramie and flax contain lower lignin percentage as compared to banana and jute fibres. This also leads to produce finer fibre by the plant during its bio-synthesis in the plant body. So, in order to produce value-added textile products, chemical processing of such fibres like pre-treatment, bleaching, dyeing, printing, finishing etc. are important and such chemical interventions has profound effect on fibre colour, feel, look, fineness and rigidity [7]. Hydrogen peroxide bleaching is conventionally carried out for discolouration/de-pigmentation of the lignocellulosic plant fibres to change their natural hue golden (dark to light) yellow to white, bright and clean fibre [10 - 12]. It also cleans the fibres which enhances their absorbency due to removal of natural and added oil, fat and waxy material from the fibre surface. The hydrogen peroxide bleaching is carried out at high alkaline condition at elevated temperature of 80–90 °C and produces very good whiteness and absorbency, but the process leads to damage of fibre to some extent. The lignocellulosic fibres are sensitive to alkaline solutions, resulting high weight loss percentage due to removal of hemicelluloses and a part of lignin macro-molecules. Recently, some work has been carried out to carry out on bleaching of lignocellulosic fibres at low temperature and mild alkaline condition to produce satisfactory whiteness without much loss of its weight as well as tensile properties [10, 13 - 15]. Peracetic acid is strong new oxidizing agent having high reactivity and may be used for bleaching on lignocellulosic fibres at milder process condition [16]. Study has been done on optimisation of peracetic (PAA) acid bleaching conditions for different lignocellulosic fibres like jute, banana, flax and ramie. The PAA is an environment friendly bleaching agent, as it is having -COOH group and it is fast acting, non-foaming, water soluble and found to be suitable for textile bleaching [17-19]. In the water bath PAA maintains equilibrium reaction with hydrogen peroxide and acetic acid, and the bleaching mechanism mainly involves epoxidation of double bonds of impurities and coloured compounds to produce white fibres. Fibre degradation is also marginal in the case of peracetic acid bleaching.

In order to make the bleaching process sustainable and economic, the bleach bath has been reused two times in the present work, so that the left out bleached bath liquor viz., oxidizing agent and auxiliary chemicals are utilized to the fullest extent. Different parameters like liquor ratio, concentration of bleaching agents, pH of the bleach bath plays an important role in bleaching hence during selection of methodology for reuse of bleach liquor both compensation of chemicals or without has been followed. Furthermore, reuse of bleach bath in the sequential bleaching would also reduce the chemical load in the discharge effluent. The physical properties and optical properties of the treated fibres were evaluated in details at different stages of processing. The bleached fibres produced thus can find application in subsequent stages of colouration in medium to dark shades for production of value-added apparel and clothing.

2. Methodology

2.1 Materials

Lignocellulosic fibres used in this study were made available from local sources, i.e., jute (*Corchorus olitorius*), Banana (*Musa domestica*), Flax (*Linum usitatissimum*) and Ramie (*Boehmeria nivea*).

2.2 Chemicals

Various chemicals of analytical grade (MERCK, India) namely, tetrasodium-pyrophosphate (TSPP) and sodium carbonate and acetic acid were used in the bleaching process. The commercial grade peracetic acid (PAA) with active CH_3COOOH of 35% (w/v) was procured from the Chemtex Speciality Limited, Kolkata, West Bengal, India with specific gravity of 1.12-1.13 g/cc and used in bleaching of jute, ramie, flax and banana fibres. Likewise, the Ultravon JU (non-ionic surface-active agent) of laboratory grade was procured from the Charminar Enterprise, Kolkata.

2.3 Mild scouring and peracetic acid bleaching

Raw jute, ramie, flax and banana fibres were initially treated with sodium carbonate (2% on weight of fibre) and non-ionic surface-active agent (Ultravon JU, 2 g/L) at a temperature of 50 °C for 30 min, keeping M.Lr ratio at 1:20. Bleaching of mild scoured lignocellulosic fibres were carried out in a closed vessel with fibre-to-water ratio of 1:30 in the presence of non-ionic surface-active agent: 0.5 ml/l, sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃): 1.8 g/l, tetrasodium pyrophosphate (TSPP): 3 g/l and, while changing the three important bleaching process parameters namely, treatment time, temperature and peracetic acid concentration depending on the optimised bleaching conditions of lignocellulosic fibres. The pH of the bleach bath was maintained at 7.5 – 8, using sodium carbonate and TSPP. Initially sodium carbonate and tetrasodium pyrophosphate (TSPP) solutions with concentrations of 1.8 g/l and 3 g/l, respectively were prepared in hot water and added in bleached bath. After bleaching, the fibres were washed thoroughly in fresh running water and finally dried in air.

Reuse of the bleach bath has been done as per process mentioned in the figure below and coding of the samples has also been done accordingly.

Figure 1 – Bleaching of different ligno-cellulosic fibres through re-use of bleach bath by various approaches

2.4 Fibre properties evaluation

i. Optical properties

Whiteness index (WI) on the ‘HUNTER’ scale and yellowness index on the ‘ASTM D 1925’ scale for all the banana fibre samples were measured by Spectrascan-5100 computerized colour matching system. Other colour parameters viz., colour strength (*K/S*), *L**, *a** and *b** were also measured in the same equipment with the presence of D65 illuminant and 10° angle of observer. Canon 5D Mark III SLR camera (Japan make) was used to illustrate the optical images of the fibres. The reported whiteness index value is the average of 5 measurements.

ii. Bundle strength

Bundle strength of banana fibre was measured after conditioning the sample in a standard atmosphere i.e., 65±2% relative humidity, 27±2° C temperature for 48 h following the BIS recommendation (IS: 6359-1971). Bundle strength was evaluated using fibre bundle strength tester, worked on the principle of beam balance (with two unequal arms) following BIS, 1986 (f) standard (Chattopadhyay et al. 2020). The reported values are the average of bundle strength of 15 fibre samples.

3. Results and Discussion

Among the different lignocellulosic fibres jute, banana, flax and ramie fibres have been well characterised and are found to be suitable for textile application either alone or in blends with other natural fibres. These fibres are composed of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, pectin as major constituents but their proportion varies from fibre to fibre, so the hygroscopicity of the fibres also varies which are tabulated in Table 1. Lignin content is more in jute and banana whereas pectin content is more in flax and ramie. Again, cellulose content is more in ramie and flax whereas jute and banana contain high hemicellulose percentage. Dimensions of ultimate cells of these fibres as

seen in Table 2 clearly show that high L/B ratio for ramie and flax makes them suitable for finer yarns whereas low L/B ratio in case of jute and banana fibres can be used for coarser yarns. Considering textile application of these fibres either in finer apparel or coarser home textiles, these fibres require chemical processing like bleaching, dyeing, finishing, etc. to make them attractive with suitable functional properties.

Table 1 - Chemical constitution of different lignocellulosic fibres [20]

Fiber	Cellulose (wt %)	Hemicellulose (wt %)	Lignin (wt %)	Waxes (wt %)	Pectin (wt %)	Moisture Content (wt%)
Flax	71	18.6–20.6	2.2	1.5	2.3	10
Jute	61–71	14–20	12-13	0.5	0.4	12.6
Ramie	68.6–76.2	13–16	0.6–0.7	0.3	1.9	8
Banana	63-67	19	5	—		8.7

Table 2 - Dimension of ultimate cells of some natural fibres [20]

Fibre	Length, L (mm)	Breadth, B (µm)	L:B ratio (average)
Jute	0.8-6	10-25	110
Ramie	20-25	15-80	3500
Flax	25-65	10-35	1700
Banana	0.9-4.0	12-33	100

Pre-treatment i.e., scouring of all these fibres were done and subjected to peracetic acid (PAA) bleaching following optimised recipe which is tabulated as in Table 3.

Table 3 - Optimized condition of different lignocellulosic fibres

Variables	Optimised condition			
	Flax	banana	Ramie	Jute
Temperature (°C)	75	73	76	75
Time (minutes)	125	135	69	127
Concentration (mL/L)	10	15.4	18	20
pH	7.8	7.5	7.0	8.0

In the present study, after bleaching of the lingo-cellulosic fibres, an effort was made to reuse of the bleach bath to reduce the effluent load along with reduction in cost of chemical involvement in bleaching. Several processes were followed for proper use of left out bleach liquor either by compensation of liquor-ratio, bleaching auxiliaries as well as bleaching agents or without compensation to achieve maximum possible bleaching effects. The left-out bleach liquor after taking out the first sample was collected and used for bleaching for another two times as per the protocol mentioned below. All the reused samples were evaluated for optical and tensile properties, which are most important for textile fibres for their application in diversified and value-added products. In this present study four different experiments were executed viz., (i) reuse of bleach bath after compensation for liquor ratio and pH, (ii) reuse of bleach bath without compensation for liquor ratio and pH. (iii) Reuse of bleach bath after compensation for liquor ratio, pH and PAA and (iv) reuse of bleach bath without compensation for liquor ratio, pH but PAA. The results of evaluation are tabulated in Tables 4-7.

3.1 Original – Bleached sample produced from Virgin bleach bath at optimised recipe

1st Batch (Reuse)

A –Reuse of bleach bath after compensation for liquor ratio and pH

A1 – Reuse of A bleach bath after compensation for pH only

2nd Batch (Reuse)

B – Reuse of bleach bath without compensation for liquor ratio and pH.

B1- Reuse of B bleach bath after compensation for liquor ratio and pH.

3rd Batch (Reuse)

C – Reuse of bleach bath after compensation for liquor ratio, pH and PAA.

C1 – Reuse of C bleach bath after compensation for pH only

4th Batch (Reuse)

D – Reuse of bleach bath without compensation for liquor ratio, pH but PAA

D1 – Reuse of D bleach bath after compensation for liquor ratio, pH and PAA.

Table 4 - Reuse of PAA bleach bath for Jute

Jute fibre	K/s	WI	YI	BI	L	a	b	B.S.
Scoured	4.10	40.3	40.2	12.6	51.8	7.8	18.0	21.2
Original	0.53	75.2	31.6	49.6	83.9	0.05	16.8	20.0
A	0.79	70.6	36.6	42.5	80.5	0.26	19.0	19.5
A1	1.20	64.4	45.1	33.8	75.7	2.79	21.4	18.4
B	0.81	69.6	36.7	41.3	79.5	0.71	18.6	20.0
B1	0.90	65.6	41.5	36.2	78.2	1.41	21.2	18.3
C	0.71	71.8	38.5	43.7	82.0	0.87	19.4	16.8
C1	0.92	68.1	40.8	38.8	78.7	1.81	20.2	15.4
D	0.75	70.8	36.1	42.7	82.3	0.57	18.8	16.7
D1	0.76	70.7	36.4	42.3	80.5	0.89	18.5	15.4

Table 5 - Reuse of PAA bleach bath for Banana fibre

Banana fibre	K/s	WI	YI	BI	L	a	b	B.S.
Scoured	1.82	57.0	33.8	26.6	68.2	5.1	18.4	28.4
Original	0.78	74.3	40.3	46.4	84.5	0.42	22.0	27.1
A	0.81	71.8	39.8	39.8	80.3	0.74	21.2	26.9
A1	1.17	68.9	45.9	38.7	80.4	1.42	24.0	26.5
B	0.84	71.4	41.1	41.6	80.8	0.27	22.7	27.1
B1	1.20	69.3	47.1	35.1	77.9	1.67	24.8	26.2
C	1.53	64.9	49.6	33.7	77.1	2.11	25.1	22.9
C1	1.34	65.0	47.4	34.1	76.8	2.28	23.5	21.6
D	1.46	63.7	45.9	33.1	75.4	1.80	22.5	20.8
D1	1.19	68.8	46.5	38.6	80.5	1.49	24.4	20.1

Table 6 - Reuse of PAA bleach bath for Ramie fibre

Ramie fibre	K/s	WI	YI	BI	L	a	b	B.S.
Scoured	1.34	55.8	28.3	26.2	66.0	4.8	14.6	22.1
Original	0.29	76.3	23.5	52.7	83.4	1.91	10.9	21.4
A	0.32	72.6	24.1	47.3	78.9	1.74	11.3	20.6
A1	0.42	71.7	25.9	43.2	77.8	2.17	11.6	19.6
B	0.30	73.2	22.7	44.1	78.1	1.64	10.8	21.6
B1	0.40	70.5	25.1	42.3	76.9	1.81	11.5	21.2
C	0.52	69.2	28.1	42.4	77.6	2.37	12.5	21.3
C1	0.47	70.8	28.4	44.3	79.1	2.61	12.7	19.9
D	0.42	71.5	24.7	45.9	77.4	1.71	11.3	21.2

Table 7 - Reuse of PAA bleach bath for Flax fibre

Flax fibre	K/s	WI	YI	BI	L	a	b	B.S.
Scoured	3.09	49.0	42.2	18.6	61.7	3.7	22.3	13.2
Original	0.78	72.0	38.0	43.8	82.2	-0.38	20.7	12.7
A	1.06	67.9	34.6	40.0	78.1	-2.32	19.0	12.2
A1	1.38	62.9	39.3	33.2	74.1	-1.15	20.1	11.8
B	0.81	70.1	34.8	41.1	79.0	-1.54	19.2	12.3
B1	1.01	67.2	39.9	37.7	78.1	0.11	20.6	11.1
C	0.83	70.2	36.0	42.2	79.3	-1.51	19.9	12.7
C1	1.23	64.9	39.5	35.1	76.0	-1.33	20.8	12.3
D	0.81	71.0	33.2	44.2	80.7	-1.33	18.0	12.1
D1	0.96	67.6	34.8	39.2	77.8	-1.54	18.54	11.3

The above tables show that reuse of the bleach bath can be done with compensation of auxiliaries and bleaching agent or without any compensation. Studies indicate that in case of all the fibres compensation of liquor and chemicals does not produce any major improvement, if optical properties but some deterioration in bundle strength for flax and ramie fibres. In some cases, addition of bleaching agent marginally improves whiteness value increasing process cost hence not recommended. So, same bleach bath can be used for 3 times. Moreover, compensation of chemicals increases cost of bleaching also. Hence considering cost of bleaching, improvement of optical properties and retention of tensile strength, 2nd batch i.e., 1st reuse can be done without any compensation, but adjustment of liquor ration and pH correction is needed during 2nd reuse for achieving satisfactory results.

4. Conclusion

Peracetic acid bleaching of jute, banana, flax, and ramie produces satisfactory whiteness index with retention of high tensile strength at optimized bleaching condition. The peracetic acid (PAA) bleach bath can be reused for two times with sufficient whiteness to be used subsequently for medium to deep shade coloration. For the 1st reuse no compensation of bleaching auxiliaries, bleaching agent (PAA) or water is needed. However, in the case of 2nd reuse bath little compensation of only water and bleaching auxiliaries are needed to maintain the liquor ratio and pH of the bath. All the fibre samples, bleached in the reused bath showed maximum retention of bundle strength. After the 2nd reuse, the achievable whiteness in the banana, flax, jute and ramie fibre are 69.3, 67.2, 65.6 and 70.5, respectively.

5. Acknowledgement

Authors would like to thank to the Director of the institute for various research aids.

References:

- [1] Samanta, K. K., Roy, A. N., Baite, H., Debnath, S., Ammayappan, L., Nayak, L. K., Singha A., & Kundu, T. K. (2023). Properties of Himalayan Nettle Fibre and Development of Nettle/Viscose Blended Apparel Textiles. *J. Nat. Fibers*, 20, 2183924. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2023.2183924>
- [2] Basak, S., Shakyawar, D. B., Samanta, K. K., Debnath, S., Bhowmick, M., & Kumar, N. (2022). Development of natural fibre based flexible composite: A sustainable mimic of natural leather. *Mater. Today Commun.* 32, 103976-103985. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2022.103976>
- [3] Roy, A. N., Samanta, K. K., Patra, K. (2019). Physico-chemical properties of black yak fibre and its modification for blending with jute fibre. *J. Nat. Fibers*, 16(2), 225-236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2017.1414652>
- [4] Sheshama, M., Khatri, H., Suthar, M., Basak, S., & Ali, S. W. (2017). Bulk vs. Nano ZnO: Influence of fire retardant behavior on sisal fibre yarn. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 175, 257-264. DOI:10.1016/j.carbpol.2017.07.032
- [5] Samanta, K. K., Basak, S., Chattopadhyay, S. K. (2016). Potential of Ligno-cellulosic and Protein Fibres in Sustainable Fashion. In: *Sustainable Fibres for Fashion Industry* (Ed. Muthu, S.S., Gardetti, M.A.), Springer Publication, vol. 2, pp.61-109
- [6] Varma, D. S. (1986). High performance organic fibres for industrial applications. *Man-Made Textiles in India*. 29, 380-86

- [7] Chattopadhyay, S.N., Pan, N.C., Roy, A.N., & Samanta, K.K. (2020). Pretreatment of jute and banana fibre – its effect of blended yarn and fabric. *J. Nat. Fibers*, 7(1), 75-83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2018.1469450>
- [8] Shahid, M., Mohammad, F., Chen, G., Tang, R-C., & Xing, T. (2016). Enzymatic processing of natural fibres: white biotechnology for sustainable development, *Green Chem.* 18, 2256-2281. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6GC00201C>
- [9] Ghosh, S., Singh, S., & Maity, S. (2021). Thermal Insulation Behavior of Chemically Treated Jute Fiber Quilt. *J. Nat. Fibers*, 18, 568-580. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2019.1636744>
- [10] Chattopadhyay, S.N, Pan, N.C., & Day, A. (2003). Pseudo single bath process for ambient temperature bleaching and reactive dyeing of jute. *Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research*, 28, 450-455
- [11] Basu, G., & Chattopadhyay, S.N. (1996). Ambient temperature bleaching of jute - its effect on mechanical properties and dyeing behaviour. *Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research*, 21, 217-223
- [12] Chattopadhyay, S.N., Pan, N.C., & Day, A. (2004). A wet processing of jute at ambient temperature. *AATCC Review*, 4: 27-27
- [13] Chattopadhyay, S.N., Pan, N.C., & Day, A. (2006). Reuse of reactive dyes for dyeing of jute fabric. *Bioresource Technology*, 97, 77-83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2005.02.033>
- [14] Pan, N.C., Chattopadhyay, S.N., & Day, A. (2004). Pseudo single bath process for alkali treatment and bleaching of jute at ambient temperature. *Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research*, 29, 79-84
- [15] Chattopadhyay, S.N., Pan, N.C., & Day, A. (2001). Bleaching of jute at ambient temperature and its reuse. *Textile Trends*, XLIII (12), 23-25
- [16] Chattopadhyay, S. N., Pan, N.C., Roy, A.N., & Samanta, K.K. (2022). Low Temperature Bleaching of Jute using Peracetic Acid: A Novel Process. *AATCC Journal of Research*, 9, 98-105. <https://doi.org/10.1177/247234442210814>
- [17] Chattopadhyay, S. N.; Pan, N. C.; Khan, A.; Bhowmick, A.; Chakraborty, S. Bleaching of jute with Per Acetic Acid, *The Indian Journal of Natural Fibre*, 2018, 4 (2), 73-79.
- [18] Duan, L.; Yu, W.; Li, Z. Analysis of Structural Changes in Jute Fibers after Peracetic Acid Treatment, *Journal of Engineered Fibers and Fabrics*, 2017, 12 (1), 33-42.
- [19] Cai, Y.; David, S. K. Low Temperature Bleaching of Jute Fabric Using a Peracetic Acid System, *Textile Research Journal*, 1997, 67 (6), 459-564.
- [20] Data Book on Fibres Allied to Jute. 2012. Published by Director-National Institute of Research on Jute and Allied Fibre Technology: 1-70